

INNOVATIVE APPROACH TO INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF USE OF ENERGY RESOURCES IN AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTION

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Abstract. *The article describes the problems of building innovative activity related to the problems of the investment process, a system of investment policy rules that would facilitate the creation of a positive investment climate in our country and allow for the active development of innovative products and technologies.*

Problems of innovative development in the agricultural sector in the Republic of Uzbekistan, which uses energy resources for innovative development, increasing productivity and reducing energy intensity.

Research results have shown that the mass introduction of innovative technologies and modern machines contribute to a significant reduction in energy consumption per unit of production. In addition to this material and technical base of many agricultural producers, the potential for reducing energy costs is significant.

Keywords: *innovation, investment, agriculture, energy resources, economics.*

Introduction. The modern economy requires active innovation to maintain competitiveness and active development. In modern times, technologies are changing very quickly, which actively influence the technical equipment of enterprises. Innovative development is directly related to investment activities. Connections with this Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 28, 2023, №166, it was approved that in order to create favorable conditions for the development of a healthy competitive environment and increase the influx of foreign and private investment in the energy sector, as well as the formation of wholesale and retail electricity markets [1].

Today, when deciding to invest in production activities, they are guided by the introduction of new equipment and technologies. It is impossible to invest in something that is already outdated, otherwise you will never be able to keep up with your competitors and successfully resist external threats and develop. As a result, it is impossible to consider these two concepts separately from each other in modern economics. If an enterprise has innovations, then it means investment is taking place; if there are investments, then they should be directed into innovative products and technologies. The unfavorable dynamics shown by the main macroeconomic indicators, the low pace of scientific and technological development, constant fluctuations in the position of the investment market, the instability of state investment policy and forms of regulation of investment activity do not make it possible in modern conditions to effectively introduce new technologies and pursue a full-fledged innovation policy.[2].

The purpose of the research. The problem today is exacerbated by the inaccessibility or high cost of many innovations, which for certain reasons are not available within the country, and their inaccessibility in foreign markets. Many modern problems of building innovative activity are associated with problems of the investment process, which are a consequence of the lack of a

precisely prepared system of investment policy rules that would contribute to the creation of a favorable investment climate in our country and allow the active development of innovative products and technologies. In this regard, the purpose of the study is to study the innovative development of productivity growth and reduction in energy intensity, which is explained by a decrease in the cost per unit of production [2,3].

Accordingly, such a system is designed to provide a unified investment space throughout the country, i.e. ensuring the free movement of financial resources, investment and innovative products.

Main part. Investment policy is directly related to innovation policy, which today is decisive for maintaining high competitiveness in existing and potential markets, which is especially important for domestic enterprises. Investments are the basis for ensuring innovation, because only on the basis of investment can one renew production assets, modernize equipment and technologies, and use the latest achievements of science and technology. It is the lag in technical equipment and the lack of high technologies in many, even leading enterprises in the country, that determines the low competitiveness of domestic enterprises, especially in the agricultural sector [3,4,5].

This circumstance also hinders the development of human resources and human potential, because without the availability of appropriate technologies and technical equipment, it is impossible to master practical knowledge in new areas, there is nowhere to apply the acquired theoretical knowledge, which in modern conditions quickly becomes outdated [2]. The state's investment policy should be aimed at creating uniform conditions for the economic and legal space for investment and innovative activities and its information support. In today's conditions, the effectiveness of investment and innovation activities of agricultural organizations largely depends on the organization of management of the organization's innovation and investment policy. Making decisions on innovative development and searching for the necessary investment resources seems to be the most difficult and main management task, as a result of which there is a need to combine the efforts of all participants in the process of managing the innovation and investment activities of an enterprise, the implementation of which is possible only through a unified investment management structure within the current organizational management structure [5,6].

One of the most important areas of innovative development in the agricultural sector is increasing the efficiency of using energy resources. In modern conditions, increasing energy efficiency seems to be the main direction for the innovative development of organizations.

Today it becomes obvious that energy resources are becoming the most important resource that determines the future development of any state. As a result, in recent decades there has been an active search for new energy sources, active development of alternative energy sources. For our country, energy intensity is a defining indicator that shows the stability of development of both the entire state and the energy industry in particular [7].

In modern conditions, the problem of insufficient resources makes it necessary for the most developed countries to find all available opportunities for innovative solutions to this issue, and first of all, in the energy sector. And in solving this problem, the most economically developed countries have achieved significant achievements using alternative and renewable energy sources. Our country lags significantly behind these countries in this direction. [1,6,7].

Currently, in our country the share of alternative energy sources occupies only 2% of the total generated volume, and by 2025 it is planned to increase this share to 4-5%, while in other countries such as Europe, this figure already exceeds 30 % average. The transition to the use of alternative energy sources is directly related to the implementation of innovative solutions in the form of the introduction of the latest technologies and technical means into production activities. [1,3,8].

From this point of view, modern innovative solutions and approaches used in many areas of the economy, including the agricultural sector, determine the energy efficiency of production, due to the solution of the problem of energy consumption and reducing resource costs for manufactured products, which determines their competitiveness. Innovations in the technological and technical spheres are the main components for increasing the efficiency of energy use in agricultural production.

Economical and efficient use of energy resources by agricultural organizations is an important condition for production costs. The problem of efficient use of energy resources is of particular importance for the agricultural industry.

In agriculture, a 20% reduction in costs due to savings in fuel and energy resources is equivalent to a 5% increase in sales volume. The energy costs of agricultural producers in our country are 4-5 times higher than other countries such as Europe and Asia. For the agricultural sector of the economy, as for other areas of the economy, there is a problem in the field of energy saving and increasing energy efficiency, which is directly related to significant depreciation of fixed assets, which directly causes significant losses in both the production and consumption of energy resources. There are universal ways to reduce and save energy consumption in different industries. These include the use of a multi-tariff electricity metering system, and compliance with modern building codes and requirements for thermal insulation of industrial buildings and structures, and the design of ventilation and lighting in industrial and other premises, temperature control in buildings, heating and water heating systems, the use of energy-saving lamps etc. On the other hand, there are standard energy-saving and energy-efficient solutions that were specifically developed for the agricultural sector of the economy. These requirements and provisions were noted in the State Program for Energy Saving and Energy Efficiency, which was adopted in 2023 and is designed for the period until 2030.

The program included proposals such as:

- 1) increasing the efficiency of agricultural machines by optimizing their power and reducing average fuel consumption, including new agricultural machines running on diesel fuel;
- 2) increasing the efficiency of using energy resources in greenhouses;
- 3) the use of variable frequency electric drives and the use of heat from exhaust gases for heating, etc.

Investments in innovative technologies in agriculture account for a significant part of the budget for agro-industrial production, which is noticeable in the growth dynamics of this indicator in developed countries. As for the domestic agro-industrial complex, investment activity in this direction is quite weak, and in some cases, there is even a decrease in funding for innovative activities.

Over the past decade, funding for various programs aimed at developing new technologies and innovative projects in the agricultural sector has decreased by more than one and a half times per 1 hectare of agricultural land. The noted factor did not allow us to fully comply with the

requirements of the State Program for Energy Saving and Increased Energy Efficiency, because had a counteracting effect on the implementation of innovative solutions.

In addition, the active introduction of innovative technologies in the agricultural sector is not entirely favorably perceived by industry workers, which is associated, on the one hand, with a significant outflow of labor resources from rural areas, as well as the need for workers to master new work methods and technologies, which requires retraining and new competencies.

As a result, in agricultural production there are largely workers who carried out their activities using old methods and technologies, and innovation is completely or partially rejected by them. The negative attitude and lack of professional personnel in agricultural enterprises increases, which is associated with the state of education in rural areas and the difficulties of obtaining vocational education. Therefore, problems often arise with young workers in agricultural enterprises in terms of a focused and professional approach to the adoption of innovations in production.

This factor is confirmed in some experiments on the organization of agricultural enterprises using modern technologies, in which production processes are automated as much as possible. As a result, the widespread introduction of innovations in the agricultural sector of the economy also presupposes the qualitative development of a full-fledged education system in rural areas, as well as the development of social infrastructure.

The mechanism involved in energy saving is formed on the basis of three main directions to reduce the energy intensity of agricultural production. These are technical, technological and organizational requirements that are rarely met in practice.

The following solutions will contribute to the effective implementation of energy conservation reserves:

- selection of energy consumption and energy saving indicators and their analysis;
- feasibility study of energy-saving processes in the field of technological and technical solutions, also applied to the production and use of alternative energy sources;
- development of measures for state support for energy saving and increasing the efficiency of energy use in production;
- development of standard rules with energy suppliers;
- development of a unified regulatory framework for the consumption of energy resources and their rational use.

In terms of the key factor in the cost of agricultural products, the indicator of which is its energy intensity (the amount of energy expended on the production of a unit of output), Russian producers of agricultural products are 3-4 times inferior to the most developed foreign producers. In this case, geographical location and climatic conditions are of great importance, but insufficient use of innovative technologies and modern equipment is of greater importance.

To increase the competitiveness of agricultural products, the main factor of which is the cost of its production, it is necessary to achieve a level of innovative development in the industry at the level of advanced countries.

The main goal of innovative development is to increase productivity and reduce energy intensity, which reduces the cost per unit of production. In terms of direction and scope of application in the agro-industrial complex, four types of innovations should be noted:

- selection and genetic;
- technical and technological;

organizational and managerial;
social and ecological.

The first type of innovation applies only to agriculture.

The most promising areas in terms of innovative development are the following:

genetic potential of animals;
technical re-equipment of the production sector;
technologies in production activities;
innovations in the management system.

The massive introduction of innovative technologies and modern machines contribute to a significant reduction in energy costs per unit of production. Due to the backwardness of the material and technical base of many agricultural producers, the potential for reducing energy costs is significant.

Main directions of energy saving in agriculture:

1. Introduction of soil cultivation technologies with minimal energy consumption.
2. Use of agriculture with high energy efficiency, consisting in low specific consumption of fuel and energy resources, high productivity, maintenance of technical serviceability, timely maintenance and updating. The introduction of an electric-powered machine and tractor fleet, the use of hybrid engines, the design of tractors and combines based on electric motors as a driving force, which eliminates environmental pollution, and reduces specific energy costs per unit of production.
3. The use of energy-saving lighting sources, ventilation, innovative thermal insulation materials in industrial premises and structures, the use of recovery systems.
4. Use of biogas plants using organic waste.
5. The use of alternative energy sources, which is especially important given the remoteness of many rural areas from power lines and gas pipelines. The use of renewable energy sources in agriculture will reduce production costs and losses from power supply failures.
6. A set of technical means and measures for the development of robotic complexes for the production of crop and livestock products using renewable and alternative energy sources as energy supply.

This is only a part of the possible solutions aimed at energy saving in agriculture, the implementation of which involves the introduction of innovative technologies. And while there are plenty of motives for energy saving, there is very little investment for its implementation. This is explained by high risks and long payback periods.

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